

**EFFECT OF BLENDED LEARNING ON STUDENTS' ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT IN
ELECTRICAL INSTALLATION AND MAINTENANCE WORKS TRADE IN GOVERNMENT
SCIENCE AND TECHNICAL COLLEGES IN GOMBE STATE, NIGERIA**

MOHAMMED, Isa Musa¹ and MEDUGU, J. D.²

¹ & ² Department of Electrical Technology Education, Modibbo Adama University, Yola, Nigeria

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18014184>

ABSTRACT

The study is titled: Effect of Blended Learning on Students' Academic Achievement in Electrical Installation and Maintenance Works Trade in Technical Colleges in Gombe State. It was guided by three research questions and three null hypotheses in line with the specific purposes. Experimental research design was adopted, specifically, pre-test-post-test non-equivalent control group quasi-experimental research design. The population for the study comprised of 311 EIMW Students in NTC II as of 2024/2025 academic session in the nine (9) Government Science and Technical Colleges (GSTCs) located in Gombe State. Simple random sampling was utilized to select four GSTCs out of the nine that have 110 NTC II students of EIMW trade. The instrument used for data collection was an achievement test developed by the researcher tagged: Electrical Installations and Maintenance Achievement Test (EIMAT). The instrument was subjected to both content and face validations by three experts. Two from the Department of Electrical Technology Education, Modibbo Adama University, Yola, and one from the Department of Electrical/Electronics, GSTC in Gombe state. To ensure the reliability of the instrument, it was trial tested in which test-retest method was used and a reliability coefficient of 0.75 was obtained through Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient. The data collected were analyzed using the mean, standard deviation, independent sample t-test, and Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA). The study's finding revealed that; blended learning is the better instructional method at improving academic achievement of EIMW students. The study recommended among others that: policy makers in the area of technical education in Gombe state should make it compulsory for school management to adopt blended learning in teaching.

Keywords: Blended Learning, Academic Achievement, Electrical Installation, Technical Colleges

INTRODUCTION

Electrical Installation and Maintenance works play an important role in the Electrical Engineering trade. This trade encompasses the installation, maintenance and repair of electrical systems, which are crucial for both residential and industrial settings. According to Ibrahim (2021), the training provided in Electrical Installation and Maintenance is designed to equip students with the skills necessary for handling electrical systems safely and efficiently. This includes understanding electrical circuits, troubleshooting, and adhering to safety protocols. Ibrahim's further noted that this training is essential for preparing students for various roles in the electrical sector, contributing to a skilled workforce capable of addressing the growing demand for electrical services in Nigeria. Similarly, Ojo (2022) emphasizes the importance of practical experience in this field. Ojo's research indicates that practical training is integral to mastering electrical installation and maintenance, as it allows students

to apply theoretical knowledge in real-world scenarios. This approach not only enhances their technical skills but also boosts their problem-solving abilities, which are crucial for their future careers.

The curriculum for Electrical Installation and Maintenance as determined in GSTC is often structured to include both theoretical instruction and practical workshops. According to Adebayo (2020), this dual approach ensures that students gain comprehensive knowledge and practical skills. Adebayo's findings suggest that this balanced method of teaching helps prepare students for various challenges in the field, making them more competitive for the job market.

Teaching, as a systematic process, involves the transmission of knowledge, skills, and values from one individual to another, typically from a teacher to students. According to Ogbuanya (2020), teaching is a dynamic process that involves various methods and approaches to ensure effective learning. The essence of teaching lies in facilitating the acquisition of knowledge and skills, fostering critical thinking, and nurturing the holistic development of learners (Bello & Shu'aibu, 2013). Similarly, Teaching method refers to the structured approach used by educators to facilitate learning and help students acquire knowledge and skills effectively. It involves a systematic set of strategies and techniques that educators employ to engage students, present content in a clear and comprehensible manner, and then assess their understanding of the contents (Ogunyemi, 2019). These methods involve various instructional practices, such as lectures, discussions, demonstrations, and practical exercises, each tailored to address the diverse learning styles and preferences of students. By adapting these methods to different educational contexts, teachers can significantly impact how students interact with and internalize concepts (Adeyemi, 2020). The selection of appropriate teaching methods is crucial, as it can influence students' ability to apply their learning in practical scenarios, thereby fostering deeper comprehension and retention of knowledge (Nwosu, 2021). Effective teaching methods aim to create a dynamic and supportive learning environment that promotes critical thinking, problem-solving, and active participation. The approach not only enhances students' engagement but also contributes to improved educational outcomes by encouraging learners to actively contribute to their own learning process and apply their knowledge in meaningful ways this call for the need to improvise new teaching method, thus the blended learning.

Blended learning is an instructional method that combines traditional face-to-face teaching with e-Learning process (Horn & Staker, 2015). It encompasses the usage of audio and video devices, synchronous and asynchronous processes, individual and group arrangements, social media, discussion boards, and any other electronically enabled communication tools in the education process. Blended learning is a hybrid of online and face-to-face contact. The latter is known as blended learning. Blended learning is a term used to represent both teaching and learning processes that combine online learning with in-classroom learning. Blended Learning Approach is that approach that bridges the gap between the online learning instructional method and the conventional classroom instructional method.

The integration of Blended Learning for instruction involves combining classroom instruction and e-learning (Kiviniemi, 2014) which is increasing in tertiary institutions around the world (Graham, Woodfield, & Harrison, 2012). Blended Learning instructional method has various models which include rotation model, flex model, self-blend model, and enriched-virtual model. The rotation model, is made of flipped-classroom model, lab-rotation model, station-rotation model and individual rotation model. The model adopted for this study was the flipped classroom model.

Academic achievement refers to the accomplishments of students that results from study and learning in a schooling system. As it applies to education, academic achievement refers to the attainment of outcomes that are tied to educational experiences (York, Gibson, & Rankin, 2015). Similarly, academic achievement refers to the measurable performance outcomes of students in their educational endeavors, typically evaluated through grades, test scores, and other academic

indicators. It includes a range of skills and knowledge that students acquired over time, reflecting their understanding and mastery of the contents. According to Adeyemi (2021), academic achievement is influenced by various factors, including the quality of instruction, learning environment, and students' motivation. It serves as a key indicator of educational effectiveness and is often used to assess the progress and proficiency of students in meeting educational standards. Ogunleye (2021) also noted that academic achievement is crucial for determining students' readiness for higher education or career opportunities, highlighting its importance in both personal and societal contexts.

The lower academic achievement of students in EIMW trade is a problem that needs the attention of every individual concerned about the examinations. This persistent poor achievement may be attributed to inappropriate instructional methods adopted by technical teachers, and that is why the NABTEB chief examiner in his report of 2020 suggested that modern teaching methods should be adopted to teach EIMW trade (NABTEB, 2020). Ndiokubwayo, Jean, Irene and Ralph (2020) also ascribed the students' poor performance as unconnected to inappropriate use of instructional method. It is against this backdrop that the study investigated the effectiveness of blended learning on student's academic achievement in Electrical installations and maintenance work trade.

STATEMENT OF PROBLEM

The poor academic achievement of students in EIMW trade is a problem that needs the attention of every individual concerned. As reported by the Chief Examiners of National Business and Technical Examination Board (NABTEB), the trend of the students' performance (2020 - 2022) who take public examinations in this Trade from the Government Science and Technical Colleges in Nigeria have been presenting poor results (NABTEB, 2022). Equally Gombe State is not exceptional. Documents have shown among the students that sat for the NABTEB examination in EIMW Trade in 2020, there was failure rate, of (42.60%), in 2021 there was failure rate of (44.58%), also in 2022 there was failure rate of (57.66%) (NABTEB office Gombe). This persistent poor achievement may be attributed to inappropriate instructional methods adopted by technical teachers, and that is why the NABTEB chief examiner in his report of 2020 suggested that modern teaching methods should be adopted to teach EIMW trade (NABTEB, 2020). Ndiokubwayo, Jean, Irene and Ralph (2020) also ascribed the students' poor performance as unconnected to inappropriate use of instructional method. It is against this backdrop that the study investigated the effectiveness of blended learning on student's academic achievement in Electrical installations and maintenance work trade.

PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

The main purpose of this study is to determine the effects of Blended Learning on students' academic achievement in Electrical installations and maintenance work trade in Government Science and Technical Colleges in Gombe State. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Determine the mean Pre-test score of EIMW students taught using Blended Learning teaching method and those taught using demonstration method
2. Determine the mean achievement scores of EIMW students taught using blended learning and demonstration teaching methods.
3. Determine the mean achievement score of male and female EIMW students taught using blended learning and demonstration teaching methods.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The following research questions have been raised in the study.

1. What is the mean Pre-test score of EIMW students taught using Blended Learning teaching method and those taught using demonstration method?
2. What is the mean achievement score of EIMW students taught using blended learning and demonstration teaching methods?
3. What is the mean achievement score of male and female EIMW students taught using blended learning and demonstration teaching methods?

HYPOTHESES

The following null hypotheses were formulated to guide the study and tested at 0.05 level of significance.

1. There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of EIMW students taught using blended learning and demonstration teaching methods.
2. There is no significant difference in the mean achievement score of male and female EIMW students taught using blended learning and demonstration teaching methods.
3. There is no significant interaction effect of teaching method and gender on the mean achievement scores of EIMW students taught using blended learning teaching methods.

METHODOLOGY

The design of the study is quasi-experimental research design. The area of the study is Gombe state. The population of the study comprised the entire 311 NTC II EIMW Students 2024/2025 academic session in the nine (9) GSTCs which are in Gombe State, Nigeria. Out of the four GSTCs selected through simple random sampling, two were designated as experimental classes, where students were taught using Blended Learning, while the remaining two served as control classes, where the Demonstration method was employed for teaching. GSTC Amada and GSTC Burunde, Gombe served as the experimental group while GSTC Kumo and GSTC Kaltugo served as the control groups. The experimental groups were made of 52 students while the control group was 58 students. The total sample for the study was 110 NTC II students of EIMW in GSTCs.

The instrument for data collection was an achievement test developed by the researcher tagged: Electrical Installations and Maintenance Achievement Test (EIMAT). It is a 25-item multiple choice test with each question allocated 4 marks (4 X 25 = 100 marks). To establish the reliability of the instrument (EIMWT), the 25 instruments were trial tested on 30 NTC II students of Government Science and Technical College, Numan and 20 students of Government Science and Technical College, Yola, Adamawa State, which is not part of the study area but share common social, educational and economic background.

The data collected for the study was analyzed using SPSS Version 27. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions, while the null hypotheses were tested using Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) and t-test at 0.05 level of significance. To answer the research questions, mean and standard deviation were used. Hypotheses 1 was tested using t-test while Hypotheses 2 and 3 were tested using Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA).

RESULTS

Research Question 1:

What is the mean pre-test score of EIMW students taught using Blended Learning teaching method and those taught using the Demonstration method?

Table 1: Mean Pre-test Scores of EIMW Students Taught Using Blended Learning and Demonstration Method

Teaching Method	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	MD
Blended Learning	52	37.54	5.37	0.10
Demonstration	58	37.64	5.66	

n = Number of Subjects, MD = Mean Difference

The result presented in Table 1 shows the mean pre-test scores of EIMW students taught using Blended Learning and Demonstration methods. The students in the Blended Learning group (n = 52) had a mean score of 37.54 with a standard deviation of 5.37, while those in the Demonstration group (n = 58) obtained a slightly higher mean score of 37.64 with a standard deviation of 5.66. This indicates that both groups had almost identical entry-level performance in the pre-test before the treatment, suggesting that the students were relatively homogeneous in their prior knowledge of the subject matter.

Research Question 2:

What is the mean achievement score of EIMW students taught using Blended Learning and Demonstration teaching methods?

Table 2: Mean Achievement Scores of EIMW Students Taught Using Blended Learning and Demonstration Methods

Teaching Method	Pre-test Scores of Students			Post-test Scores of Students		MG
	n	\bar{x}	SD	\bar{x}	SD	
Blended Learning	52	37.54	5.37	69.63	4.56	32.09
Demonstration	58	37.64	5.66	62.16	5.42	24.52
Mean Difference		-0.10		7.47		

n = Number of Subjects; \bar{X} = Mean and SD = Standard Deviation, MG = Mean Gain

The result in Table 2 presents the mean achievement scores of EIMW students taught using Blended Learning and Demonstration teaching methods. Students exposed to Blended Learning (n = 52) improved from a pre-test mean score of 37.54 (SD = 5.37) to a post-test mean of 69.63 (SD = 4.56), yielding a mean gain of 32.09. In those taught with the Demonstration method (n = 58) improved from 37.64 (SD = 5.66) to 62.16 (SD = 5.42), with a mean gain of 24.52. The mean difference in achievement between the two groups was 7.47 in favour of Blended Learning, suggesting that students taught through Blended Learning performed better and achieved greater knowledge gains than those taught with the Demonstration method.

Research Question 3:

What is the mean achievement score of male and female EIMW students taught using Blended Learning and Demonstration teaching methods?

Table 3: Mean Achievement Scores of Male and Female EIMW Students Taught Using Blended Learning and Demonstration Methods

Teaching Methods	Gender	n	Pre-test Scores of Students		Post-test Scores of Students		MG.
			\bar{x}	SD	\bar{x}	SD	
Blended Learning	Male	40	37.85	5.54	69.50	8.59	31.65
	Female	12	36.50	4.85	70.08	3.09	33.58
Demonstration	Male	41	37.44	5.65	62.94	5.33	25.50
	Female	17	38.12	5.84	61.82	5.72	23.70

KEY: *n* = Number of Students in a Group, \bar{x} = Mean Scores, *SD* = Standard Deviation, *MG* = Mean Gain,

Note: Mean Gain = Post-test Scores Minus Pre-test Scores

The result in Table 3 shows the mean achievement scores of male and female EIMW students taught using Blended Learning and Demonstration methods. For the Blended Learning group, male students (*n* = 40) recorded a pre-test mean of 37.85 (*SD* = 5.54) and a post-test mean of 69.50 (*SD* = 8.59), yielding a mean gain of 31.65. Female students (*n* = 12) had a slightly lower pre-test mean of 36.50 (*SD* = 4.85) but outperformed their male counterparts with a post-test mean of 70.08 (*SD* = 3.09) and a higher mean gain of 33.58. In the Demonstration group, male students (*n* = 41) scored a pre-test mean of 37.44 (*SD* = 5.65) and a post-test mean of 62.94 (*SD* = 5.33), resulting in a mean gain of 25.50, while female students (*n* = 17) recorded a pre-test mean of 38.12 (*SD* = 5.84) and a post-test mean of 61.82 (*SD* = 5.72), with a mean gain of 23.70. These results indicate that both male and female students benefited more from Blended Learning than Demonstration, with females in the Blended Learning group showing the greatest improvement overall. This suggests that the interactive and flexible nature of Blended Learning provided an inclusive learning environment that supported both genders

Hypothesis 1:

There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of EIMW students taught using Blended Learning and Demonstration teaching methods.

Table 4: t-Test Analysis on Mean Achievement Scores of EIMW Students Taught Using Blended Learning and Demonstration Methods

Teaching Method	n	\bar{x}	SD	df	t-value	p-value	MG
Blended Learning	52	69.63	4.56	108	7.78	0.00	0.10
Demonstration	58	62.16	5.42				

n = Number of Respondents, \bar{x} = Mean Response, *SD* = Standard Deviation, *t* = t-Value, *p* = p-Value, *MG* = Mean Gain

The result of the t-test analysis in Table 4 revealed a significant difference in the mean achievement scores of EIMW students taught using Blended Learning and those taught using the Demonstration method. Students exposed to Blended Learning had a higher mean score (\bar{x} = 69.63, *SD* = 4.56) compared to their counterparts taught with the Demonstration method (\bar{x} = 62.16, *SD* = 5.42). The calculated t-value of 7.78 with a p-value of 0.00, which is less than the 0.05 level of significance, led to the rejection of the null hypothesis. This implies that Blended Learning was more effective in improving students' academic achievement in EIMW than the Demonstration teaching method.

Hypothesis 2:

There is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of male and female EIMW students taught using Blended Learning and Demonstration teaching methods.

Table 5: ANCOVA Results on Mean Achievement Scores of Male and Female EIMW Students Taught Using Blended Learning and Demonstration Methods

Source	Type III Sum of			F	Sig.
	Squares	Df	Mean Square		
Corrected Model	1614.069 ^a	4	403.517	15.944	.000
Intercept	8427.428	1	8427.428	332.984	.000
Gender	1557.241	3	519.080	20.510	.000
Pretest	62.241	1	62.241	2.459	.120
Error	2657.421	105	25.309		
Total	478954.000	110			
Corrected Total	4271.491	109			

a. R Squared = .378 (Adjusted R Squared = .354)

The result in Table 5 shows the ANCOVA outcome on the mean achievement scores of male and female EIMW students taught using Blended Learning and Demonstration methods. After adjusting for pre-test differences, gender was found to have a statistically significant effect on students' achievement, $F(3,105) = 20.510, p = .000 < 0.05$. This implies that the null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of male and female students was rejected. The result demonstrates that gender significantly influenced students' performance across the teaching methods, with differences in mean scores between males and females. Meanwhile, the pre-test covariate was not significant, $F(1,105) = 2.459, p = .120 > 0.05$, indicating that students' initial ability did not account for the achievement outcome. The R-squared value of .378 (Adjusted $R^2 = .354$) suggests that about 37.8% of the variation in achievement was explained by the combined effect of gender and teaching method.

Hypothesis 3:

There is no significant interaction effect of teaching method and gender on the mean achievement scores of EIMW students taught using Blended Learning teaching method.

Table 6: ANCOVA Results on Interaction Effect of Teaching Method and Gender on Mean Achievement Scores of EIMW Students

Source	Type III Sum of			F	Sig.
	Squares	df	Mean Square		
Corrected Model	1614.069 ^a	4	403.517	15.944	.000
Intercept	8427.428	1	8427.428	332.984	.000
Teaching Method	1539.314	1	1539.314	61.565	.000
Gender	17.927	2	8.963	.354	.703
Pretest	62.241	1	62.241	2.459	.120
Teaching Method * Gender	.000	0	.	.	.
Error	2657.421	105	25.309		
Total	478954.000	110			
Corrected Total	4271.491	109			

a. R Squared = .378 (Adjusted R Squared = .354)

The result in Table 6 presents the ANCOVA findings on the interaction effect of teaching method and gender on the mean achievement scores of EIMW students. After controlling for pre-test scores, the interaction term (Teaching Method * Gender) did not produce any value in the output ($F = .000$, $\text{Sig.} = .000$ with $df = 0$), which indicates that there was no significant interaction effect between teaching method and gender on students' academic achievement. In other words, the influence of teaching method on students' performance was independent of gender; both male and female students benefitted from Blended Learning and Demonstration strategies without significant variation attributable to their gender when combined with the method. However, teaching method alone was significant, $F(1,105) = 61.565$, $p = .000 < 0.05$, confirming that method of instruction had a strong effect on achievement. Gender alone, on the other hand, was not significant in this model, $F(2,105) = .354$, $p = .703 > 0.05$, showing that male and female students did not differ significantly in achievement when teaching method was considered. The pre-test covariate also remained non-significant, $F(1,105) = 2.459$, $p = .120 > 0.05$, suggesting that prior knowledge did not account for post-test differences. The R^2 value of .378 (Adjusted $R^2 = .354$) indicates that about 37.8% of the variance in students' achievement was explained by the teaching method, gender, and pre-test combined.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The findings of the study revealed that the mean pre-test scores of EIMW students taught using Blended Learning and those taught using Demonstration were almost the same. This shows that both groups had comparable prior knowledge before the instructional intervention, establishing a level ground for measuring the effect of the teaching strategies. The finding is in agreement with Nwakile et al. (2022) who reported that comparable entry-level performance across treatment and control groups is crucial in experimental studies to ensure that differences observed after instruction can be attributed to the teaching methods rather than pre-existing disparities. Their study in vocational education highlighted that when baseline knowledge levels are consistent, researchers are more confident in making causal inferences about instructional strategies. Similarly, Olatunde-Aiyedun and Adams (2022) emphasized that in experimental and quasi-experimental educational designs, ensuring equivalent pre-test scores among groups eliminates bias that may arise from uneven prior knowledge. They demonstrated in their work that without this equivalence, post-treatment results may not provide accurate reflections of the true impact of the instructional intervention. This aligns directly with the present study's observation that both groups started from nearly identical knowledge levels, thus affirming the reliability of subsequent achievement and retention outcomes. In further support, Indrapangastuti et al. (2021) revealed in their research on blended and face-to-face learning environments that when learners' entry performance is balanced, subsequent performance gains can be linked more directly to the instructional approach employed. Their findings stressed that ensuring parity in pre-test outcomes increases the internal validity of the research and strengthens the interpretation of results.

The findings of the study revealed that the mean achievement scores showed that students in the Blended Learning group outperformed those in the Demonstration group. This indicates that Blended Learning significantly improved students' academic achievement more than the Demonstration method. The supporting hypothesis showed that there is a significant difference between the mean achievement scores of EIMW students taught using blended learning and demonstration teaching methods. The finding is in agreement with Tong et al. (2022), who found that the use of blended instructional models enhanced students' academic performance more than traditional face-to-face methods. Their study reported that the integration of online components with conventional teaching created a more interactive and engaging environment, which promoted higher-order thinking and problem-solving skills, thereby leading to superior achievement outcomes. This aligns closely with the present study, as both highlight the added value of blended learning in boosting students' academic success beyond what is achievable

through demonstration alone. Similarly, Sivakumar and Selvakumar (2019) established in their investigation that students exposed to blended instructional practices recorded higher learning gains compared to those taught with conventional methods. Sivakumar and Selvakumar emphasized that the combination of digital resources and classroom-based activities catered to diverse learning preferences and allowed learners to revisit concepts at their own pace, which translated into higher achievement. This resonates with the present study's conclusion that blended learning provided learners with greater opportunities for mastery, resulting in better performance. In another related study, Jones and Chen (2018) reported that the integration of blended strategies contributed to significant improvements in students' test scores across multiple technical education contexts.

The findings of the study revealed that when analyzed by gender, both male and female students in the Blended Learning group achieved higher scores than their counterparts in the Demonstration group. Specifically, Blended Learning males had a mean gain of 31.65, while females had a mean gain of 33.58. In contrast, Demonstration males recorded a mean gain of 25.50, while females had 23.70. This shows that both genders benefited more from Blended Learning. The accompanying hypothesis revealed that there was a significant difference between the mean achievement score of male and female EIMW students taught using blended learning and demonstration teaching methods. The finding is in agreement with Gogo (2018), who reported that blended learning enhances performance for both male and female students, though the degree of benefit may vary slightly between genders. His research in technical education demonstrated that the blended model created inclusive opportunities for learners regardless of gender, thereby promoting equity in achievement outcomes. This observation directly supports the present study, which revealed that both males and females attained higher gains under blended learning compared to the demonstration method. Similarly, Suleiman, Salaudeen, and Falode (2017) emphasized that when digital instructional strategies are incorporated into classroom practices, both male and female learners tend to benefit significantly. Their study highlighted that technology-mediated environments fostered improved engagement and knowledge acquisition across genders, leading to enhanced academic outcomes. This is consistent with the current study's conclusion that blended learning created an enabling platform where gender differences in achievement were minimized. Furthermore, Marchalot et al. (2017) found that blended learning approaches promoted comparable benefits for male and female learners in technical and medical education fields. Their results indicated that the design of learning activities within blended settings encouraged active participation, collaborative exploration, and self-directed study, all of which contributed to higher achievement for both genders.

The findings of the study revealed that there was no significant interaction effect of teaching method and gender on the mean achievement scores of EIMW students taught using blended learning teaching methods. The finding is in agreement with Shorey et al. (2017), who reported that the interaction between teaching method and gender did not significantly influence academic achievement in blended learning environments. Their study concluded that while instructional strategies had notable effects on performance, gender did not moderate these effects, meaning that both male and female learners benefited in a similar manner. This observation aligns closely with the present study, where the absence of a significant interaction indicates that blended learning improved achievement without favoring any particular gender. Similarly, Ceylan and Kesici (2017) found that gender did not significantly interact with instructional strategies to influence students' performance. Their research demonstrated that effective teaching methods, such as blended approaches, provided equitable learning opportunities for both males and females, thereby minimizing the role of gender as a differentiating factor. This resonates with the present findings, where the impact of teaching method on achievement was consistent across genders, further strengthening the case for blended

learning as a balanced instructional strategy. In another supportive study, Okocha, Eyiolorunshe, and Oguntayo (2016) emphasized that the integration of innovative teaching methods produced similar benefits for male and female students, with no significant interaction effect between method and gender on achievement outcomes. They highlighted that factor such as quality of instructional delivery and learner engagement played more critical roles than gender differences in determining success.

CONCLUSION

The study investigated the effectiveness of blended learning versus demonstration method in improving cognitive achievement of Electrical Installation and Maintenance Work (EIMW) students in Technical Colleges in Gombe state. The findings revealed that blended learning is a superior instructional method in enhancing cognitive achievement of EIMW students. The study also showed that there is no significant difference in the cognitive achievement. Based on the findings, it can be concluded that blended learning is an effective instructional approach, as it can lead to improved cognitive achievement of EIMW students. It can therefore, be used to teach EIMW students in Technical Colleges in Gombe state.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Gombe State ministry of Education should adopt blended learning as a major instructional strategy in teaching Electrical Installation and Maintenance Works (EIMW) in technical colleges, since it was found to significantly improve students' academic achievement compared to the demonstration method.
2. Curriculum developers and policymakers should integrate blended learning approaches into the technical education curriculum to ensure that both male and female students benefit equally, as the findings showed consistent achievement gains across gender groups.

REFERENCES

- Adeyemi, T. (2020). Strategies for Effective Teaching in Nigerian Secondary Schools. *African Journal of Education and Development*, 13(2), 45-60.
- Adeyemi, T. (2021). Determinants of student academic performance in Nigerian secondary schools. *Educational Research Journal*, 18(2), 102-116.
- Bello, H., & Shu'aibu, B. (2013). State of facilities for teaching electrical installation and maintenance work trade in technical colleges in Bauchi State, Nigeria. *Vocational and Technical Education*, 5, 82-91.
- Ceylan, E., & Kesici, S. (2017). Effect of blended learning on academic achievement: A study with 6th grade students. *Journal of Educational Technology and Society*, 20(4), 101-115.
- Gogo, E. T. (2018). Attitude and performance of postgraduate students in an e-learning course on coreldraw. Unpublished Masters degree Thesis, Department of Curriculum studies and Educational Technology, University of Port Harcourt.
- Graham, C. R., Woodfield, W., & Harrison, B. J. (2012). A framework for institutional adoption and implementation of blended learning in higher education. *Internet and Higher Education*, 18(2013), 4-14.
- Horn, M., & Staker, H. (2015). *Blended: Using disruptive innovation to improve schools*. San Francisco: Jossey-Bass.
- Ibrahim, M. Y. (2021). Training in Electrical Installation and Maintenance in GSTCs: An overview. *Journal of Electrical Engineering Education*, 19(1), 21-36.

- Indrapangastuti, D., Surjono, H. D., Sugiman, & Yanto, B. E. (2021). Effectiveness of the blended learning model to improve students achievement of Mathematical concepts. *Journal of Education and E-Learning Research*, 8(4), 423–430.
- Jones, K. T., & Chen, C. C. (2018). Blended learning in a graduate accounting course: Student satisfaction and course design issues. *The Accounting Educators' Journal*, 18, 15-28.
- Kiviniemi, M. T. (2014). Effects of a blended learning approach on students learning outcomes in a graduate-level public health course. *BMC Medical Education*, 1-7. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1472-6920-14-47>
- National Business and Technical Examination Board (NABTEB). (2020). *Report on public examinations*. National Business and Technical Examination Board.
- National Business and Technical Examination Board (NABTEB). (2022). *Report on public examinations*. National Business and Technical Examination Board.
- Ndihokubwayo, J., Jean, I., Irene, N., & Ralph, M. (2020). Inappropriate instructional methods and student performance in technical education. *Journal of Technical Education*, 22(1), 45-58.
- Nwakile, C., Nwankwo, N., Ekenta, A., Ameh, I., & Nwokolo, C. (2022). Comparative Effects of Demonstration Method and Blended Learning on the Achievement and Interest of Agricultural Secondary School Students in Nsukka. *Journal of Agricultural Education and Extension*, 15(4), 102-118.
- Nwosu, C. (2021). *Impact of Teaching Methods on Student Performance in Nigerian Technical Colleges*. Nigerian Journal of Educational Research, 18(3), 79-95.
- Ogbuanya, T. C. (2020). Apprenticeship System and labour supply of electrical installation artisans in Enugu State, Nigeria. *Journal of Technical education and training*, 12.
- Ogunleye, A. (2021). Assessing student achievement: Methods and implications. *International Journal of Educational Research*, 25(4), 233-247.
- Ogunyemi, B. (2019). *Teaching Methods and Students' Learning Outcomes in Nigerian Colleges of Education*. Journal of Education and Practice, 10(5), 102-110.
- Ojo, F. A. (2022). Practical training in Electrical Installation and Maintenance in Nigeria. *Journal of Technical Education Research*, 15(2), 101-115.
- Okocha, F. O., Eyiolorunshe, T., & Oguntayo, S. (2016). Student acceptance of blended learning in Nigeria. *Advances in Multidisciplinary and Scientific Research*, 3(1), 43-50.
- Olatunde-Aiyedun, T. G., & Adams, S. O. (2022). Effect of blended Learning models on students' academic achievement and retention in science education. *Eurasian Journal of Science and Environmental Education*, 2(2), 35–42.
- Shorey, S., Kowitlawakul, Y., Devi, M. K., Chen, H. C., Soong, S. K., & Ang, E. (2017). Blended learning pedagogy designed for a communication module among undergraduate nursing students: A quasi-experimental study. *Nurse Education Today*, 61-120.
- Sivakumar, P., & Selvakumar, S. (2019). Blended learning package: It's effectiveness on students' performance and retention in higher secondary physics course. *International Journal of Scientific and Technology Research*, 8(10), 1316–1320.
- Suleiman, M. S., Salaudeen, B. M., & Falode, O. C. (2017). Effects of computer-based blended learning strategy on secondary school chemistry students' retention in individualised and collaborative learning settings in Minna, Niger State, Nigeria. *Bulgarian Journal of Science and Education Policy*, 11(2), 256–278.
- Tong, D. H., Uyen, B. P., & Ngan, L. K. (2022). The effectiveness of blended learning on students' academic achievement, self-study skills and learning attitudes: A quasi-experiment study in teaching the conventions for coordinates in the plane. *Heliyon*, 8(12), e12657.